

SAR Tomography Reconstruction using ISTA and GLRT Techniques

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Abstract—SAR Tomography (TomoSAR) leverages the utilization of multiple baselines to gather data about an area, enabling the acquisition of information not only in the range-azimuth direction but also in the elevation direction. This additional information in the elevation direction primarily consists of point scatterers, with one or more scatterers typically present within a single resolution cell. This research paper examines two distinct methodologies for detecting multiple scatterers in TomoSAR: the conventional Generalized Likelihood Ratio Test (GLRT) technique and a compressive sensing (CS) approach known as the Iterative Soft-Thresholding Algorithm (ISTA). The results are examined for a simulated case of two scatterers and a real case using the TerraSAR-X dataset.

Index Terms—SAR Tomography(TomoSAR), SAR reconstruction, compressive sensing (CS) SAR, GLRT, ISTA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) takes advantage of the ability to synthesize a long antenna along the azimuth direction, typically aligned with the flight direction of the sensor, to achieve a focused beam. This produces a two-dimensional image containing information along the range and azimuth directions. To analyze information in three dimensions, SAR tomography (TomoSAR) was introduced in the early 1990s [1]. The term *tomography* is quite misleading as it links to computed axial tomography which utilizes large range of angles but TomoSAR utilizes very small angular diversity and exploits the concept of multibaseline interferometry to create a synthetic aperture in the elevation direction.

In conventional SAR, the synthetic aperture in the azimuth direction introduces a variation in the squint angle, while the synthetic aperture in the elevation direction is associated with variations in the off-nadir angle [1]. TomoSAR takes advantage of multiple data stacks acquired from slightly different viewing angles of the same area. The interferometric data stacks, acquired from approximately the same orbit, are then utilized for persistent scatterer interferometry (PSI). Every pixel within an interferogram is defined by its range and azimuth coordinates, along with the temporal and spatial baselines of the corresponding interferogram. These four coordinates facilitate a more thorough data analysis in comparison to a single interferogram that has fixed temporal and spatial baselines. PSI is a methodology for long-term subsidence monitoring

in urban areas. These persistent scatterers are typically small, manmade features and offer millimeter level precision in case of deformation monitoring in urban areas [9]. PSI exploits point scatterers with strong radar backscatter, which exhibit high correlation over an extended time period, to provide a phase history of the target point over time [2]. The objective of SAR tomography is to reconstruct the reflectivity profile of scatterers in the elevation direction, which essentially involves solving a spectral estimation problem.

In [10], [11], the conventional Generalized Likelihood Ratio Test (GLRT) based detection technique is used for presence of single and double scatterers. In the context of PSI, this detector has demonstrated superior performance when compared to traditional detectors [12], [13].

The elevation aperture length used in the TomoSAR model has very limited extent and often leads to a poorer elevation resolution. Hence, super resolution algorithms are proposed for SAR tomography [14], [15]. In one range-azimuth bin, the presence of scatterers are considered small and sparse leading to the introduction of compressive sensing (CS) in SAR tomography [12]. CS based techniques such as Sparse Bayesian Learning (SBL) [2], alternating direction method of multipliers (ADMM)-based L1 algorithm [16], truncated singular valued decomposition (TSVD) based CS [17] and Iterative Soft Thresholding Algorithm (ISTA) [18] are considered to be state of the art for resolving scatterers in TomoSAR. The main drawback of CS technique is the high computational load.

In this paper, we analyze the detection capabilities of GLRT and CS method, ISTA for the presence of scatterers. We initially utilize simulated data for TomoSAR to detect the presence of one or more scatterers in a resolution cell. These methods are further applied to a real data tomographic model using high-resolution spotlight TerraSAR-X data, which comprises 40 data stacks. This dataset offers a detailed depiction of the urban structures in Cologne. The analysis of Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI) was conducted using the interferometric point target analysis (IPTA) framework [5]–[8] of GAMMA software. The reconstruction results will be assessed based on the algorithms' capability to detect the presence of one or more scatterers within a resolution cell.

II. TOMOSAR IMAGING MODEL

A. Tomography System Model

The main focus of the tomography model is to resolve the scatterers in the third dimension i.e., the elevation direction orthogonal to the azimuth-range plane of the SAR sensor. The model is extensively derived in [3], [4], offering a thorough explanation of the fundamental principles. In this context, we present the final equation derived from the model. From Fig. 1, N complex SAR datasets of the same area are obtained from different orbit positions.

Fig. 1. TomoSAR imaging geometry. The sensor acquires data from different positions, $P_1 - P_5$ of the same scene. ρ_r is the range resolution and ρ_z is the elevation resolution

The focused complex value, denoted as y_n , for an azimuth-range pixel in the n^{th} acquisition at the aperture position b_n (where n ranges from 1 to N) can be obtained by integrating the reflected signal along the elevation direction and applying a linear phase term as a weighting factor:

$$y_n = \int_{\Delta s} \gamma(s) \exp(-j2\pi\xi_n s) ds \quad (1)$$

where $\gamma(s)$ is the reflectivity of the scatterer and Δs is the elevation extent. The spatial frequency is denoted by $\xi_n = \frac{2b_n}{\lambda R_0}$ where R_0 is the range to the scene center. The model presented in eq. (1) is approximated by discretizing the reflectivity function along s with the presence of noise ϵ .

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\boldsymbol{\gamma} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N)^T$ is $N \times 1$ measurement vector, $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times N}$ is $N \times M$ mapping matrix with $A_{nm} = \exp(-j2\pi\xi_n s)$, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ is the discrete reflectivity vector of size M with $\gamma_m = \gamma(s_m)$ and $s_m (m = 1, \dots, M)$ are discrete elevation positions.

The Rayleigh range resolution of SAR is given by, $\rho_r = c/2B$ where c and B are the speed of light and the bandwidth of the SAR system, respectively. The elevation resolution can

be formulated as, $\rho_z = \lambda R_0 / 2L_x$ where L_x is the synthetic aperture in elevation (see Fig. 1).

The inversion of the model as seen in Eq. (2) helps retrieve the elevation information of one or more scatterers present in a single resolution cell.

III. INVERSION METHODOLOGY

The model defined in Eq. 2 is a highly underdetermined problem i.e., for $N \ll M$, there exist an infinite number of solutions. Many parametric and non-parametric algorithms have been proposed and tested for this model and the parametric methods have known to produce a much higher accuracy in the presence of multiple scatterers [2]. For our analysis, we present two algorithms for detecting the presence of a scatterer: GLRT and ISTA

A. Generalized Likelihood Ratio Test (GLRT)

For the case of GLRT, we introduce the following hypotheses: \mathcal{H}^0 - presence of no stable scatterer, \mathcal{H}^1 - presence of a single scatterer, \mathcal{H}^2 - presence of a double scatterer.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}^0 : \mathbf{y} &= \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \\ \mathcal{H}^1 : \mathbf{y} &= \gamma_1 \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{s}_1) + \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \\ \mathcal{H}^2 : \mathbf{y} &= \gamma_1 \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{s}_1) + \gamma_2 \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{s}_2) + \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where, $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{s})$ is the steering vector which can also be represented as:

$$\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{s}) = [1 \quad e^{-j2\pi\xi_1(\mathbf{s})} \quad \dots \quad e^{-j2\pi\xi_{N-1}(\mathbf{s})}]^T \quad (4)$$

The reflectivity is estimated by a beamformer (BF) is given as:

$$\hat{\gamma}(\mathbf{s}) = \frac{1}{N} \mathbf{a}^H(\mathbf{s}) \mathbf{y} \quad (5)$$

Assuming the presence of atleast one scatterer (\mathcal{H}^1 or \mathcal{H}^2 to be true), the estimated absolute reflectivity can be formulated as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_1 = \arg \max_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{S}} (|\hat{\gamma}(\mathbf{s})|) \quad (6)$$

The estimated parameters for the first scatterer are determined by finding the global maximizers of the merit function within the set \mathbb{S} , which encompasses all possible height information. The estimated energy of first scatterer is given by:

$$E_1 = \frac{|\hat{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_1)|^2}{\|\mathbf{y}\|^2} \quad (7)$$

To distinguish the second scatterer, the estimated backscatter contribution from the first scatterer is subtracted from the SLC (Single-Look Complex) vector [10] to obtain the difference \mathbf{y}_d . This subtraction is performed to prevent any misinterpretation of the sidelobe of the first scatterer as a separate and distinct second scatterer.

$$\mathbf{y}_d = \mathbf{y} - \hat{\gamma}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_1) \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{s}_1) = \hat{\mathbf{S}}_1^\perp \mathbf{y} \quad (8)$$

where,

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}}_1^\perp = \mathbf{I}_N - \frac{1}{N} \|\mathbf{a}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_1)\|^2 \quad (9)$$

The estimate of the second scatterer is obtained by the application of a beamformer based maximization:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_2 = \arg \max_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{S}} \left(\frac{|\mathbf{a}^H(\mathbf{s})\mathbf{y}_d|}{\|\hat{\mathbf{S}}_1^\perp \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{s})\|} \right) \quad (10)$$

The second reflectivity estimate of the scatterer is calculated using a beamformer employing the CLEAN algorithm [21] [22]. This is give by,

$$E_2 = \frac{|\mathbf{u}_d^H \mathbf{y}_d|^2}{\|\mathbf{y}_d\|^2} \quad (11)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{u}_d = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{S}}_1^\perp \mathbf{a}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_2)}{\|\hat{\mathbf{S}}_1^\perp \mathbf{a}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_2)\|} \quad (12)$$

The estimated reflectivity of the first and second scatterer is

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\gamma}_1 &= \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_1)\mathbf{y} \\ \hat{\gamma}_2 &= \mathbf{a}^H(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_2)\mathbf{y}_c / \|\hat{\mathbf{S}}_1^\perp \mathbf{a}(\hat{\mathbf{s}}_2)\|. \end{aligned}$$

The normalised energies E_1 and E_2 are compared against thresholds T_1 and T_2 respectively. Initially a pixel is checked if it consists of a double scatterer or not i.e., \mathcal{H}_2 or $\bar{\mathcal{H}}_2$ respectively,

$$E_2 \underset{\mathcal{H}_2}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_2}{\geq}} T_2.$$

If not a double scatterer then it is tested for the hypotheses \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_0 .

$$E_1 \underset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\geq}} T_1.$$

To maximize the probability of detection of both single and double scatterers, the thresholds were chosen as $T_1 = T_2$ [10].

B. Iterative Soft Thresholding Algorithm (ISTA)

A popular $L_2 - L_1$ norm minimization CS technique known as Iterative Soft Thresholding Algorithm (ISTA) [19] is used to tackle the inversion problem. The minimization problem is represented as,

$$f(\gamma) = \underset{\gamma}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\gamma\|_2^2 + \mu\|\gamma\|_1 \quad (13)$$

As the name suggests, a soft thresholding operator, t_η for each coefficient of z is chosen such that,

$$t_\eta(z) = \begin{cases} z - \eta \operatorname{sign}(z) & \text{if } |z| > \eta \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

and $T_\eta(\mathbf{z})$ the vector with t_η applied to each coefficient of \mathbf{z} . ISTA is a modified gradient method:

$$\nabla f(\gamma) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \gamma} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\gamma\|_2^2 = -2\mathbf{A}^H(\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\gamma) \quad (15)$$

Algorithm 1 ISTA (Iterative Soft Thresholding Algorithm)

Require: Measurement vector \mathbf{y} , Sensing matrix \mathbf{A} , Initial estimate γ_0 , Step size parameter μ

Ensure: Estimated signal γ

- 1: Set iteration counter k to 0
 - 2: **repeat**
 - 3: Increment the iteration counter: $k \leftarrow k + 1$
 - 4: Compute the residual: $\mathbf{r}_k \leftarrow \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\gamma_k$
 - 5: Compute the gradient of the objective function: $\nabla f(\gamma_k) \leftarrow \mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{r}_k$
 - 6: Update the estimate of the signal using soft thresholding: $\gamma_{k+1} \leftarrow t_\eta((\gamma_k + \mu \nabla f(\gamma_k)))$
 - 7: Check convergence criteria
 - 8: **until** convergence criteria satisfied
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IV. RESULTS

The initial analysis is performed on a simulated case. The parameters for the simulated case is presented in the following table: The model is examined under two scenarios:

TABLE I
PARAMETERS CONSIDERED FOR SIMULATED CASE.

Parameters	Value
Range to scene center, r_0	847.36 km
Wavelength, λ	0.056m
Scatterer 1 position, s_1	0m
Scatterer 2 position, s_2	120m
Scatterer 1 amplitude, a_1	1
Scatterer 2 amplitude, a_2	0.8

one without noise and the other with the presence of additive white Gaussian noise. The signal is intentionally contaminated with noise, and the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is set to 4.24 dB.

A. Simulated Data

In this case, a total of 40 baselines were selected, which were utilized both in the real scenario and the simulated scenario. The distribution of these baselines can be observed in Fig. 4, with the reference baseline highlighted in red. The resulting elevation resolution for this case is 15.23m. In the simulated scenario, two scatterers were positioned at 0m and 120m, with amplitudes of 1 and 0.8 respectively.

Fig. 2 illustrates the estimated normalized power spectrum of the scatterers for noiseless case for both the GLRT and ISTA methods. In the case of GLRT, aside from the main lobe, there are additional side lobe contributions that can potentially lead to false alarms. This effect is predominantly caused by the uneven distribution of baselines, which has been extensively discussed in [4]. On the other hand, ISTA maximizes the contributions of the scatterers while suppressing the side lobes. As a compressive sensing (CS) algorithm, ISTA capitalizes on the concept of signal sparsity and the limited number of scatterers present in the elevation plane. In Fig. 3, the presence of noise results in the reflectivity spectrum of the scatterers being almost concealed by the sidelobes in the GLRT case.

Fig. 2. GLRT and ISTA results for signal without noise.

Fig. 3. GLRT and ISTA results signal with noise.

Conversely, ISTA distinctly detects the scatterers even in the presence of noise, albeit with compromised signal amplitudes. The regularization parameter μ , has to be carefully chosen in order to obtain efficient results. The results also depend on the step size of the elevation extent and is chosen much less than ρ_z .

B. Real Data

The dataset utilized in this case was acquired from TerraSAR-X in high-resolution spotlight mode. The sensor provides a slant range resolution of up to 0.6m, which corresponds to a bandwidth of 300MHz and a spatial resolution of up to 1m. The study area focuses on the city of Cologne, Germany, characterized by numerous man-made structures that are suitable for persistent scatterer analysis. A preprocessing step involved uses a stack of 40 single look complex (SLC) images. These images were captured over a period of 2 years, from May 2012 to November 2014. To ensure accurate registration,

a section of the scene was selected and oversampled by a factor of 2. The pixel spacing in the range and azimuth directions is 0.454m and 0.870m respectively. The total size of the elevation aperture is 669.36m, resulting in an elevation resolution of 15.23m. A reference layer was selected from the SLC stack

Fig. 4. Distribution of perpendicular and spatial baselines.

for geocoding purposes. To ensure accurate coregistration, all layers were geocoded using the multilook intensity image of the reference layer [19], [20]. Initially, a list of potential point scatterer candidates was compiled based on their high temporal stability and low spectral diversity. Subsequently, a set of differential interferograms was generated. To reduce the computational burden, an adaptive point density reduction strategy was employed to further refine the list of scatterer candidates [6]. In order to mitigate issues related to regression fitting, the atmospheric phase screen (APS) was estimated and subtracted from the differential interferograms. Through multiple iterations, the APS was isolated and removed from the data resulting in a final list of point scatterer candidates.

Fig. 5. Reflectivity estimate of scatterers for real data.

For our analysis, we have chosen a cell containing multiple

Fig. 6. TomoSAR results of Cologne.

Fig. 7. Map of detected second scatterers using GLRT.

scatterers as an example. The first scatterer is estimated to be about 97 m according to GLRT, as shown in Fig. 5. However, the reflectivity of the second scatterer is obscured by noise and sidelobes. In the case of ISTA, the scatterers are estimated at heights of 58m and 97m, respectively. The height estimation matches to the ground truth. In contrast to the GLRT algorithm, ISTA successfully identifies both scatterers by effectively reducing the impact of noise. To validate the results, we compared the height estimates with the ground truth obtained from the Digital Elevation Model from TanDEM-X, which was also used for geocoding. Additionally, in Fig. 6, we provide an overview of the scatterers found in a particular area of Cologne. We only evaluated estimated height values in the range of 35 to 150 m, since only these values are suitable for this scene. The results for GLRT and ISTA are almost the same for single scatterers.

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 illustrate the identification of double scatterer points in real data using both GLRT and ISTA. Three times more double scatterers were detected with ISTA than with GLRT. This is mainly due to the fact that in the estimated height profile of the beamformer, neighboring targets superimpose, thus influencing both the shape and the position of the maxima.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we employed the conventional GLRT and a CS method, ISTA to reconstruct the reflectivity profile of scatterers and detect the presence of multiple scatterers within a single resolution cell. GLRT utilized hypotheses to identify single and double scatterers in a scene, while ISTA approached the same problem as a minimization problem. To validate the

Fig. 8. Map of detected second scatterers using ISTA.

performance of both methods, a simulated model was utilized to confirm the presence of two scatterers under both noiseless and noisy conditions. The results demonstrated the efficacy of both methods in detecting scatterers in these scenarios. Hence, this was extended to the real case for the TerraSAR-X dataset. It can be concluded that ISTA maximises the reflectivity of the scatterers by suppressing noise. A limitation of the CS

approach is the high computational demand.

To explore further advancements in scatterer reconstruction, it would be valuable to evaluate alternative techniques like Basis Pursuit Denoising and Turbo-ISTA and assess their performance in reconstructing scatterers. This would provide insights into the effectiveness and potential applications of these methods in the context of scatterer analysis and layover situations.

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